

Determination of Mercury in Soil by Cold Vapour AAS after its Separation with Aliquat-336

SUPRA BANDYOPADHYAY and ARABINDA K. DAS*

Department of Chemistry, University of Burdwan,
Burdwan-713 104

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A large number of methods are available for the determination of mercury in trace and ultratrace level by cold vapour atomic absorption spectrophotometry (AAS). Interferences due to various ions have been reported¹⁻³. High molecular weight amines have been widely used for the extraction of various metal ions as anionic complexes^{4,5}. Liquid anion-exchanger like Aliquat-336 has been used earlier^{6,7} for the separation of vanadium, uranium and tin.

In the present work, Aliquat-336 in chloride form has been selectively used for extraction of mercury as $\text{Hg}(\text{Ox})_2^{2-}$ in toluene medium. The method has been successfully applied for determination of mercury in soil samples.

Experimental

Aliquat-336 (Fluka, A.G.) was used. Standard solution of mercury was prepared by dissolving HgCl_2 (E. Merck, G.R.) and standardised complexometrically. All other chemicals used were of analytical grade and all aqueous solutions were made using double-distilled water. A Shimadzu 646 atomic absorption spectrophotometer with MVU-1A unit was used with the following conditions: mercury hollow cathode lamp current, 5 mA; wavelength, 253.7 nm; slit width, 3.8 Å, air-flow rate, 1.5 dm³ min⁻¹. The pH values were measured with a Sambros 335 digital pH-meter.

General procedure: The aqueous phase was made up from a 0.5 ml working solution containing 20 µg of mercury. A 0.01 M oxalic acid solution (2 ml) was added and pH of the resulting solution was adjusted to 2.4. Then the aqueous phase was made up to ~10 ml and equilibrated with 5% (w/v) Aliquat-336 in toluene (10 ml) for 5 min, settled for 30 min and the aqueous phase was separated carefully. From the organic phase the metal ion was back-extracted with 6 M HNO_3 (2 × 5 ml). To the combined aqueous phase 1 N H_2SO_4 (40 ml) was mixed and 10% SnCl_2 solution (2 ml) was added to reduce Hg^{II} to the elemental state just before the run in the AAS. The absorbance was measured against the reagent blank.

Treatment of soil sample: To powdered and dried soil sample (3–4 g), concentrated HNO_3 (16 ml) and concentrated H_2SO_4 (4 ml) were added. The mixture was refluxed for 4 h on a heating mantle in a Bethge's apparatus⁸ at ~200°. The resulting solution was cooled, filtered and the

volume made up to 100 ml. An aliquot was taken and analysed for mercury after converting to its oxalate complex, adjusting the pH to 2.4 and following the general procedure.

Results and Discussion

Optimisation of different parameters: The effect of pH was investigated on the extraction of $\text{Hg}(\text{Ox})_2^{2-}$ with Aliquat-336. It was observed that extraction was quantitative over the pH range 2.1–2.6. The working pH was fixed at 2.4 by using potassium hydrogen phthalate buffer. Quantitative extraction of mercury complex occurs with toluene (100%) and extractions with other solvents show 82% in xylene, 79% in benzene, 73% in chloroform, 60% in cyclohexane, 47% in methyl isobutyl ketone, 46% in amyl alcohol, 24% in n-butyl alcohol. Thus toluene was used in the present work and no emulsion was formed during the separation. The effect of extractant concentration was studied by varying the concentration of Aliquat-336 from 0.004 M to 0.210 M using toluene as diluent. It was found that the extraction increased with increasing extractant concentration and was complete at 0.105 M liquid exchanger. The extraction and back-extraction times were varied from 1 min to 10 min; 5 min was sufficient in both the cases. The two layers were allowed to settle for 30 min.

Separation from various ions: The separation of mercury (2 µg) from mixtures of various ions was studied (within an error of ±2%) using the general procedure. The results are as follows for the binary mixtures (amount in µg in parenthesis): Cu^{II} , Fe^{III} , Al^{III} , Mn^{II} , Mg^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , W^{VI} (500 each); Zn^{II} (400); Mo^{VI} (350); Cd^{II} , Ba^{II} (250 each); Ca^{II} (200); V^{V} (50); silicate, chloride, acetate (500 µg); phosphate, formate (250 each); arsenate, sulphite, thiosulphate, thiocyanate (250 each); bromide, citrate, tartarate (100 each); and for the ternary mixtures: Co^{II} (200) + Zn^{II} (200); molybdate (50 µg) + vanadate (50); silicate (100) + phosphate (100); arsenate (100) + thiosulphate (50); Cd^{II} (100) + Ba^{II} (100); thiocyanate (50) + chloride (50); Al^{III} (200) + Ca^{II} (100).

Nature of extracted species: The molar concentration of the liquid anion-exchanger was determined by stripping the chloride by sodium hydroxide solutions and than titrating the chloride with standard AgNO_3 solution using K_2CrO_4 as an indicator.

Hg^{II} forms negatively charged complex with oxalic acid⁹. The extraction of $\text{Hg}(\text{Ox})_2^{2-}$ is quantitative provided the Aliquat-336-mercury mole ratio is ≥ 2. Plot of log *D* against log [Aliquat-336] at fixed pH provides a straight line with slope around 2. Thus the simple extraction mechanism of Hg^{II} may be represented as

where o is organic phase, a the aqueous phase and R_4N^+ is Aliquat-336.

Analysis of mercury in soil samples : The present method has been applied for the determination of mercury in several soil samples of Attri, Orissa. The results by the recommended procedure are as follows : sample-1 (81 ± 1 ppm), sample-2 (110 ± 3 ppm), sample-3 (108 ± 3 ppm), sample-4 (156 ± 4 ppm) and sample-5 (102 ± 2 ppm). The reliability of the present method was checked by studying the analytical recovery of mercury. The results for such determinations were found to be 96–103%.

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Spectrophotometric Determination of Iron(II) using Cacotheline

A. SARKAR, P. K. PARIJA* and S. K. MAJUMDAR
Department of Chemistry, North Bengal University,
Darjeeling-784 430

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CACOTHELIN is to be the nitrate of the bisdimethylmononitrobrucine hydrate¹ and have the formula, $C_{20}H_{20}(OH)_2(NO_2)_2N_2O_3 \cdot HNO_3$. Aqueous solution of cacotheline gives a violet colour with stannous ions due to the formation of a reduction product of cacotheline of unknown composition². Potluri³ used cacotheline as an indicator in estimating Pb^{IV} and Cr^{VI} with Ti^{III} . The present authors noted that Fe^{II} gives a violet colour with aqueous solution of cacotheline in presence of phosphoric acid, and which lead to the development of a simple spectrophotometric method for iron(II) determination.

Experimental

Spectral curves and analytical measurements were made with a Shimadzu PR1 spectrophotometer

fitted with quartz cells of 10 mm optical path-length.

Stock solution of iron(II) was prepared from $FeSO_4 \cdot (NH_4)_2SO_4$ and standardised⁴; a working solution was prepared by appropriate dilution. Aqueous solution of cacotheline (0.2%) was used for colour development. All other reagents were of analytical grade. Stock solutions of diverse ions were prepared from their corresponding salts.

General procedure : To an aliquot containing 100–500 μg iron(II), was added phosphoric acid (5 ml) and the aqueous solution of cacotheline (0.5 ml). Volume of the mixture was made up to 10 ml with distilled water and the absorbance of the solution was measured at 530 nm against pure water as blank. Amount of iron(II) was computed from a calibration curve. To test the interference, the respective foreign ions were added to the system before addition of the reagents.

Results and Discussion

In presence of fluoride or phosphate, iron(II) gives a violet colour with cacotheline. In the former, the colour is very unstable and fades away within 5 min. But in presence of phosphoric acid the system gives a stable colour for at least 12 h showing a broad band of absorption maxima around 530 nm. The reagent blank does not absorb in this region.

It has been noted that 0.5 ml of 0.2% cacotheline is sufficient for maximum colour development of the sample solution containing upto 500 μg of iron(II) provided the aqueous solution be made 6–10 M with respect to phosphoric acid. Lower values in absorbance were obtained when the aqueous phase was less than 5 M with respect to phosphoric acid. Higher concentration of the reagent or the acidity of the aqueous phase were devoid of any significant change in the maximum value of absorbance. The system conforms to Beer's law over the concentration range 2–50 ppm of Fe^{II} with Sandell's sensitivity of $0.05 \mu g \text{ cm}^{-2}$ at 530 nm.

To test the interferences, iron(II) was determined in presence of the respective foreign ions. Deviation of not more than $\pm 3\%$ from the expected absorbance was taken as the standard tolerance limit for the system. It was found that 300 μg of Fe^{II} could easily be determined without any interference in presence of 5 mg of each of the following cations: Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Mo^{VI} , Pd^{II} , Pt^{IV} , Rh^{III} , Cd^{II} , Ca^{II} , Ba^{II} , Sr^{II} , Zr^{II} , Th^{IV} , Be^{II} , Zn^{II} , Hg^{II} , Mg^{II} , Pb^{II} , Tl^{I} , U^{VI} , La^{III} and Al^{III} . Cu^{II} and V^{V} must be absent as the system gives no colour in presence of the said cations. Presence of less than 2 mg of Cr^{III} is harmless. In presence of Fe^{III} low absorbance is obtained. The system tolerates 50 mg of each of the following anions: EDTA, thiosulphate, iodide, bromide, fluoride, citrate, tartrate, ascorbate, oxalate, acetate, phthalate, borate. There is no colour development if nitrate is present.